

CFD analysis of the wind loads on the 'T' plan building structure including interference condition by using ANSYS CFX

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Abstract - Buildings and other structures, including all components shall be designed and constructed to resist the wind loads as required by wind codes. Simple quasi-static treatment of wind loads, which is universally applied to the design of low to medium-rise structures, can be erroneously underestimated for the design of high-rise structures. Dynamic response, vortex, and wind directionality from other structures are all complicated key factors that are supposed to be considered in design. Meanwhile, wind tunnel testing is expensive, difficult and sometimes inaccurate, even if it is a widely used method for simulation of aerodynamic response. Therefore, this study is based on CFD method using ANSYS CFX. In this study, a 'T' shaped high-rise building of 69 meters in height is studied for the mean pressure coefficient (C_p) on the building at different wind incidence angles from 0° to 180° at an interval of 30° . This model is also studied for the various interferences caused by varying distances, such as $b/2$, b , $3b/2$, and $2b$. The height of the building is taken as 69 m, and the width (b) is taken as 20 m. which are further converted for analysis in ANSYS CFX by using the 1:300 scale for the model.

Keywords - Wind load, high-rise building, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), wind effect, wind incidence angle, mean pressure coefficient.

I. INTRODUCTION

The majority of practical fluid flows are turbulent with many complex flow features that may contain recirculation zones and flow stagnation points. In the realm of wind engineering, many flow types are also present. Due to the complexity of wind flow, all the research and design work undertaken in this field has concentrated on the use of full-scale and wind tunnel analysis. This has involved the use of expensive wind tunnels and data recording facilities and has required significant time and effort to obtain the desired results. However, during the 1970's and 1980's there was a great deal of interest among the engineering community in a relatively new technique known as computational fluid dynamics (CFD). The advances made in high-speed digital computer technology had enabled the solution of flow problems, which were described mathematically by a set of coupled nonlinear partial differential equations and the appropriate boundary conditions, in a relatively short space of time and for a low financial cost. Initially, the wind engineering community largely ignored this technique due to the need for powerful computers and the errors in early modelling techniques. However, the rapidly falling costs of computer hardware and further advances in technology in the late 1980's and early 1990's enabled CFD to be applied to the complex field of wind engineering.

The 'T' plan building model that is going to be analyzed is created in ANSYS CFX. It can be done with the tools available in ANSYS, which are the Design Modeler and Space Claim Direct Modeler tools. The model can also be created in other available design software, such as AutoCAD, SolidWorks, and others, and then imported into the geometry in ANSYS. But the domain is needed to be created in the Design Modeler in case of wind load analysis. Domain works as the wind tunnel in which the model to be analyzed is placed.

Wind tunnel tests were carried out on models of a T plan shape tall building to evaluate the wind loads generated, namely base shear (F_x), overturning moment (M_y), and torsional moment (M_z), in isolated as well as interference conditions. For the isolated condition, measurements were made for many wind incidence angles, and considering the effects of interference; the interfering model has the same shape and dimensions as that of the instrumented model. The models were placed in a side-by-side as well as a tandem configuration, and the spacing between these models varied. It was observed that the presence of a neighboring building greatly affects the wind flow pattern around a building, which causes changes in the wind loading of the building. Depending on the position of the interfering building, the interference effects may either be beneficial or have an adverse effect [5].

A series of wind tunnel studies were conducted for numerous structures, including the Pentagon, T, C, and L. Finding the aerodynamic coefficient, which comprises the drag, lift, and torsional moment coefficients, is the main aim of the Ravinder's study. The building models are evaluated for several wind angles, including 0° , 45° , 90° , 135° , and 180° , while the wind tunnel is run at a wind speed of 10 m/s [10].

Sinha et al. investigated the wind pressure coefficients (C_p), four distinct spacing conditions, and seven different wind incidence angles at intervals of 30° using CFD simulations. The Interference Difference (ID) and the Interference Factor (IF) for each of the configurations under consideration were calculated using the results. The author also examined the differences in IF along the direction of the roof. Also computed and their changes examined were the drag and lift force coefficients. The primary objectives of the author's study are the evaluation of interference factors and the analysis of the variation of wind effects on low-rise pitched roof structures with one side left open to the wind environment under various interference conditions caused by varying the spacing in full blockage configurations. The numerical simulations are carried out using Ansys CFX fluid flow solver through a conventional $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model because there are no provisions in the wind standards for use in constructing such structures [7].

The variation of pressure at the faces of the octagonal plan-shaped tall building due to the interference of a three-square plan-shaped tall building of the same height is analyzed by the computational fluid dynamics module, namely ANSYS CFX, for a 0° wind incidence angle only. All the buildings are closely spaced (the distance between two buildings varies from $0.4h$ to $2h$, where h is the height of the building). Different cases depending upon the various positions of the square plan-shaped buildings are analyzed and compared with the octagonal plan-shaped building in an isolated condition [13].

II. OBJECTIVE

In this study, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) method is used for the analysis of G+22 high rise buildings of 'T' shape as shown in Fig. 1, dimensions of which are as shown in Fig. 2. The objective is to interpret the results in terms of the pressure coefficient values (from pressure contours) and velocity streamlines obtained for proposed design models. Since IS: 875 (Part III) – 2015 gives a range of deflection for pressure coefficient for simple cross-section shapes therefore the CFD study of the building is required to calculate the pressure coefficient for various shapes and wind incidence angles.

Fig. 1. Cross section of 'T' shape building

Fig. 2. Cross section of 'T' shape building with dimensions

III. 'T' PLAN BUILDING ANALYSIS UNDER ISOLATED CONDITION

In 'T' plan building studies, building prototype parameters are converted for the models to be analyzed in the software using a specific scale given in Table I below:

TABLE I
Dimensions for prototype and model for 'T' plan building

Parameter	Prototype (m)	Model (mm)	scale
Length	12.5	41.67	1:300
Width	20	66.67	
Total Height	69	230	

In this study, we analyze the 'T' plan building in order to find out the mean pressure coefficient (C_p) at different wind incidence angles, which varies from 0° to 180° at the 15° interval in clockwise direction. The faces of the building and direction of the 0° wind incident angle are shown in the Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. 'T' plan building with naming of all Faces

3.1. Geometry Modelling:

The modelling part is done in the Design Modeler tool available in the ANSYS Workbench computer software. The ZX plane is selected for the building plan, and dimensions are given to the building plan according to the calculated model parameter in Table 1. Then the domain is created around the building for wind flow, and the building is placed at 5H distance from the inlet and all 3 domain walls and at 15H distance from the domain outlet. Then the building is extruded at 230 mm model height, and the domain is extruded according to the 5H height, which is equal to 1150 mm. Material is added to the building, but the domain is taken as frozen. Then the rotation is given to the domain, as the building is not rotating to change the wind attack on different faces from different directions.

3.2. Meshing:

Then the face sizing of the building is given as 0.009 m, and the face sizing of the ground is given as 0.08 m. After that, the edge sizing of the building is given as 0.005 m, and an inflation of 30 layers is given around the building. The method of meshing is selected as automatic, and the element size of the mesh is given as 0.02 m for the rest of the domain. After generating the mesh, the tetrahedron elements are created, and nodes are generated under the 5,12,000 number limit of the ANSYS student version. The meshing of domain and the building are shown in the Fig. 4 and Fig. 5.

Fig. 4. Domain meshing of 'T' plan building

Fig. 5. Meshing of 'T' plan building

3.3. Setup:

It is a very important step of the analysis because all the parameters for wind flow and pressure are defined here. First, all the boundaries of the domain and building are defined. The material is air at 25°C, and the fluid is continuous, according to the domain flow settings. The domain model reference pressure is 1 atm, the buoyancy of the model is non-buoyant, and the domain motion is set to stationary. The fluid model is selected as K-ε in turbulence in the case of high-rise buildings. The flow analysis type is steady-state.

Power law expression: It is introduced for the calculations of pressure and to provide the velocity of wind according to the real conditions and IS 875: part 3 – 2015.

Expression is,

$$\text{Power law} = u_{\text{ref}} \left(\frac{Y}{Y_{\text{ref}}} \right)^{\alpha} \quad (1)$$

Where, $u_{\text{ref}} = 10 \text{ m/s}$, $Y_{\text{ref}} = 1 \text{ m}$, $\alpha = 0.147$

The plot of the velocity vs. height is given in the Fig. 6. and the setup for the 15° wind incidence angle of the analysis is shown in the Fig. 7.

Fig. 6. Power law graph plot

Fig. 7. Setup of the 'T' plan building analysis

3.4. Solution:

After setup, the solution of the analysis is done in the ANSYS CFX Solver Manager. The solution of the analysis stops after 50 iterations.

3.5. Results:

All the results are then found in the ANSYS CFD post. The pressure contours of every face of buildings are defined here, and the number of contour lines on each face is selected as 25. The horizontal and vertical streamlines are calculated by creating the planes where the streamlines are required.

Coefficient of pressure formula: It is calculated from the formula of drag force.

Drag force, $F_d = 0.5 \cdot C_d \cdot A \cdot V_r^2 \cdot \rho_{air}$

Where, C_d = coefficient of drag, A = area of surface, V_r = reference velocity, and

Density of air, $\rho_{air} = 1.21 \text{ kg/m}^3$

coefficient of pressure is,

$$C_p = \frac{P}{0.5 \rho V_r^2} \quad (2)$$

where pressure (P) is calculated with the help of contour lines on each face of the building model and the number of pressure points are selected accordingly. The mean pressure coefficient for all the faces of the building is represented in Table II.

TABLE II
Mean pressure coefficient on different faces of 'T' plan building

Wind Angles	Faces							
	Face A	Face B	Face C	Face D	Face E	Face F	Face G	Face H
0°	+0.382	-0.425	-0.243	-0.260	-0.221	-0.259	-0.245	-0.431
30°	+0.337	-0.393	-0.242	-0.244	-0.263	-0.310	-0.367	-0.482
60°	+0.058	-0.355	-0.238	-0.243	-0.342	-0.121	-0.293	+0.261
90°	-0.418	-0.234	-0.251	-0.243	-0.427	+0.344	+0.325	+0.360
120°	-0.293	-0.239	-0.308	-0.345	-0.528	+0.423	+0.443	+0.110
150°	-0.262	-0.326	-0.202	-0.389	+0.111	+0.445	+0.450	-0.450
180°	-0.246	-0.419	+0.274	+0.215	+0.468	+0.220	+0.283	-0.406

For a 0° wind incidence angle, maximum positive pressure occurs at Face A, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face A is found to be +0.382, and maximum negative pressure occurs at Face H, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face H is found to be -0.431, which is shown in Fig. 8.

For a 30° wind incidence angle, maximum positive pressure occurs at Face A, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face A is found to be +0.337, and maximum negative pressure occurs at Face H, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face H is found to be -0.482, which is shown in Fig. 9.

For a 60° wind incidence angle, maximum positive pressure occurs at Face H, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face H is found to be +0.261, and maximum negative pressure occurs at Face B, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face B is found to be -0.355, which is shown in Fig. 10.

For a 90° wind incidence angle, maximum positive pressure occurs at Face H, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face H is found to be +0.360, and maximum negative pressure occurs at Face E, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face E is found to be -0.427, which is shown in Fig. 11.

For a 120° wind incidence angle, maximum positive pressure occurs at Face G, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face G is found to be +0.443, and maximum negative pressure occurs at Face E, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face E is found to be -0.528, which is shown in Fig. 12.

For a 150° wind incidence angle, maximum positive pressure occurs at Face G, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face G is found to be +0.450, and maximum negative pressure occurs at Face H, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face H is found to be -0.450, which is shown in Fig. 13.

For a 180° wind incidence angle, maximum positive pressure occurs at Face E, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face E is found to be +0.468, and maximum negative pressure occurs at Face B, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face B is found to be -0.419, which is shown in Fig. 14.

3.5.1. Pressure Contours:

The pressure contours of the 'T' plan building are represented here for different wind incidence angle from 0° to 180° at interval of 30° .

Fig. 8. Pressure contours of a T-plan building under 0° wind incidence angle

Fig. 9. Pressure contours of a T-plan building under 30° wind incidence angle

Fig. 10. Pressure contours of a T-plan building under 60° wind incidence angle

Fig. 11. Pressure contours of a T-plan building under 90° wind incidence angle

Fig. 12. Pressure contours of a T-plan building under 120° wind incidence angle

Fig. 13. Pressure contours of a T-plan building under 150° wind incidence angle

Fig. 14. Pressure contours of a T-plan building under 180° wind incidence angle

3.5.2. Horizontal Streamlines:

The horizontal velocity streamlines at 0.115 mm height i.e., mid-height of the building model of the ‘T’ plan building are represented here for different wind incidence angle varying from 0° to 180° at 30° interval.

Figs. 15-21 show the boundary line separation of wind flow for the wind incidence angles of 0°, 15°, 30°, 45°, 60°, 75°, 90°, 105°, 120°, 135°, 150°, 165°, and 180°, respectively, at the mid-height of the building. At all the wind incidence angles, different horizontal velocity streamlines formed in T-plan building analysis.

Fig. 15. Horizontal streamlines at 0° wind incidence angle

Fig. 16. Horizontal streamlines at 30° wind incidence angle

Fig. 17. Horizontal streamlines at 60° wind incidence angle

Fig. 18. Horizontal streamlines at 90° wind incidence angle

Fig. 19. Horizontal streamlines 120° wind incidence angle

Fig. 20. Horizontal streamlines at 150° wind incidence angle

Fig. 21. Horizontal streamlines at 180° wind incidence angle

3.5.3. Vertical Streamlines:

The vertical velocity streamlines at side plan of the center of the building model of the 'T' plan building is represented here for every wind incidence angle from 0° to 180° at 30° interval.

Figs. 22-28 show the boundary line separation of wind flow for the wind incidence angles of 0°, 30°, 60°, 90°, 120°, 150°, and 180°, respectively, at the side plan of the building model. At all the wind incidence angles, different vertical velocity streamlines formed in T-plan building analysis.

Fig. 22. Vertical streamlines at 0° wind incidence angle

Fig. 23. Vertical streamlines at 30° wind incidence angle

Fig. 24. Vertical streamlines at 60° wind incidence angle

Fig. 25. Vertical streamlines at 90° wind incidence angle

Fig. 26. Vertical streamlines at 120° wind incidence angle

Fig. 27. Vertical streamlines at 150° wind incidence angle

Fig. 28. Vertical streamlines at 180° wind incidence angle

IV. 'T' PLAN BUILDING ANALYSIS UNDER INTERFERENCE CONDITION

In this study, the two T-plan buildings are analyzed in order to find out the mean pressure coefficient (C_p) of both buildings at a wind incidence angle of 0° by varying the distance between buildings as $b/2$, b , $3b/2$, and $2b$. where b is the width of the building model and is equal to 66.67 mm. The faces of both buildings and the direction of 0° wind incident angles are shown in Fig. 29.

Fig. 29. Interference effect of T-plan building

The mean pressure coefficient for all the faces of main building is represented in the Table III and for all faces of interference building is presented in Table IV.

TABLE III
Mean pressure coefficient of main building in 'T' plan interference

Faces	Distance between two buildings			
	$b/2$	b	$3b/2$	$2b$
Face A	+0.324	+0.327	+0.331	+0.335
Face B	-0.514	-0.506	-0.461	-0.433
Face C	-0.320	-0.316	-0.278	-0.251
Face D	-0.325	-0.331	-0.290	-0.265
Face E	-0.310	-0.281	-0.257	-0.230
Face F	-0.338	-0.319	-0.298	-0.264
Face G	-0.331	-0.306	-0.283	-0.251
Face H	-0.535	-0.501	-0.471	-0.438

TABLE IV
Mean pressure coefficient of interference building in 'T' plan interference

Faces	Distance between two buildings			
	$b/2$	b	$3b/2$	$2b$
Face A1	-0.356	-0.334	-0.262	-0.191
Face B1	-0.228	-0.189	-0.164	-0.125
Face C1	-0.167	-0.136	-0.117	-0.099
Face D1	-0.178	-0.141	-0.119	-0.095
Face E1	-0.155	-0.123	-0.104	-0.092
Face F1	-0.178	-0.140	-0.119	-0.094
Face G1	-0.169	-0.135	-0.119	-0.100
Face H1	-0.234	-0.193	-0.167	-0.126

For $b/2$ interspacing between T-plan buildings, maximum positive pressure occurs at Face A, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face A is found to be +0.324 and maximum negative pressure occurs at Face H, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face H is found to be -0.535 in the main building, which is shown in Fig. 30. In interference building, there is no positive pressure in any condition, so the maximum negative pressure occurs at Face A1, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face A1 is found to be -0.356; the minimum negative pressure occurs at Face E1, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face E1 is found to be -0.155, which is shown in Fig. 31.

For b interspacing between T-plan buildings, maximum positive pressure occurs at Face A, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face A is found to be +0.327, and maximum negative pressure occurs at Face B, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face B is found to be -0.506 in the main building, which is shown in Fig. 32. In interference building, there is no positive pressure in any condition, so the maximum negative pressure occurs at Face A1, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face A1 is found to be -0.334; the minimum negative pressure occurs at Face E1, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face E1 is found to be -0.123, which is shown in Fig. 33.

For 3b/2 interspacing between T-plan buildings, maximum positive pressure occurs at Face A, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face A is found to be +0.331, and maximum negative pressure occurs at Face H, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face H is found to be -0.471 in the main building, which is shown in Fig. 34. In interference building, there is no positive pressure in any condition, so the maximum negative pressure occurs at Face A1, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face A1 is found to be -0.262; the minimum negative pressure occurs at Face E1, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face E1 is found to be -0.104, which is shown in Fig. 35.

For 2b interspacing between T-plan buildings, maximum positive pressure occurs at Face A, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face A is found to be +0.335, and maximum negative pressure occurs at Face H, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face H is found to be -0.438 in the main building, which is shown in Fig. 36. In interference building, there is no positive pressure in any condition, so the maximum negative pressure occurs at Face A1, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face A1 is found to be -0.191; the minimum negative pressure occurs at Face E1, and the mean pressure coefficient at Face E1 is found to be -0.092, which is shown in Fig. 37.

4.2. Pressure Contours:

The pressure contours of the ‘T’ plan building interference analysis are represented here for different inter spacing between main building and rear side interference building.

Fig. 30. Pressure contours of T-plan main building at b/2 distance

Fig. 31. Pressure contours of T-plan interference building at b/2 distance

Fig. 32. Pressure contours of T-plan main building at b distance

Fig. 33. Pressure contours of T-plan interference building at b distance

Fig. 34. Pressure contours of T-plan main building at $3b/2$ distance

Fig. 35. Pressure contours of T-plan interference building at 3b/2 distance

Fig. 36. Pressure contours of T-plan main building at 2b distance

Fig. 37. Pressure contours of T-plan interference building at 2b distance

4.3. Horizontal Streamlines:

The horizontal velocity streamlines at 0.115 mm height i.e., mid height of the building models of the ‘T’ plan building interference is represented here for different inter spacing between main building and rear side interference building.

Figs. 38-41 show the boundary line separation of wind flow for the two-building interspacing's of $b/2$, b , $3b/2$, and $2b$, respectively, at the mid-height of the building. At all the interspacing's, different horizontal velocity streamlines are formed, and vortex size increases with interspacing changes, respectively, in 'T' plan building interference analysis.

Fig. 38. Horizontal Streamlines at $b/2$ distance

Fig. 39. Horizontal streamlines at b distance

Fig. 40. Horizontal Streamlines at $3b/2$ distance

Fig. 41. Horizontal streamlines at $2b$ distance

4.4. Vertical Streamlines:

The vertical velocity streamlines at side plan of the center of the building model of the 'T' plan building interference analysis is represented here for different inter spacing between main building and rear side interference building.

Figs. 42-45 show the boundary line separation of wind flow for the two-building interspacing's of $b/2$, b , $3b/2$, and $2b$, respectively, at the side plan of the building model. At all the interspacing's, different vertical velocity streamlines are formed, and vortex size increases with interspacing changes, respectively, in 'T' plan building interference analysis.

Fig. 42. Vertical streamlines at $b/2$ distance

Fig. 43. Vertical streamlines at b distance

Fig. 45. Vertical streamlines at $2b$ distance,

V. Conclusion

- The wind pressure is maximum where the wind is impacted on the large surface area of the building faces. which is also can be seen through the pressure contours of the building faces.
- CFD is a superior option for high-rise structure wind study than other common techniques like wind tunnel testing because it requires less time and money.
- A good alternative to traditional methods of predicting wind-related phenomena on buildings and other types of structures is computational fluid dynamics (CFD). With the aid of CFD simulation, boundary layer separation can be properly shown.
- The mean pressure coefficient in the interference case increases on the rear side of the building, where the distance between buildings increases. At higher interspacing, the coefficient of pressure in the rear side building is positive, and at lower interspacing, the coefficient of pressure in the rear side building is negative.
- The interference condition can also be analyzed for different wind incidence angles for future studies of the wind load in case of high-rise buildings.

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